

Green strategies in analytical chemistry

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Abstract : The literature on the green strategies in analytical chemistry is comprehensively reviewed. The bottleneck of almost every analytical scheme is the sample pretreatment. This article presents the green strategies taken up by the chemists to overcome this problem. The subject matter of the review also includes the step by step green strategic schemes in the analyses of toxic metal ions and chemicals. The discussion encompasses direct determination of solid samples, solvent elimination strategy and waste detoxification.

Keywords : Review, green strategy, green pretreatment, solventless extraction, waste detoxification.

Introduction

Analytical methodologies for the determination of hazardous substances often lead to other environmental problems because of the chemicals used or due to the wastes formed in the procedure. Therefore, it is necessary to improve the existing methodologies. Keeping this in mind the chemists are making an effort to develop alternative green analytical methods (Fig. 1). In discussing aspects of making analytical chemistry "greener", Namieśnik first used the term "green analytical chemistry" (GAC)¹. Ac-

Fig. 1. Concern in GAC (based on search results at www.sciencedirect.com).

ording to analytical chemists, green analytical chemistry can be defined as development of new methods that reduces or replaces hazardous materials used in the process or generated by the system².

Today green analytical chemistry has emerged as the new area in analytical chemistry which is based only on those "Green Chemistry Principles" which are related to analytical chemistry. Waste prevention, use of safer chemicals, design for energy efficiency, reduction of derivatives, real-time analysis for pollution prevention, inherent safe chemistry for accident prevention are some of the "Principles of Green Chemistry" that are applicable to analytical chemistry³⁻⁸. However, one should keep in mind that the new strategies should be developed in a way so as not to affect the key analytical features like sensitivity, accuracy and precision. For greening of the whole analytical procedure starting from sample preparation to its determination, new techniques are being developed which are simple, economic, clean, fast, efficient and automated.

Since green analytical chemistry is receiving increasing attention as an important area in chemistry and chemists are trying to implement green strategies in chemical education. Scientists with green mentality have taken up strategies that encompass methods for sample pretreatment, direct measurement of solid samples, solvent

elimination methodologies and waste treatment. The challenge is, therefore, to fulfill the needs of chemists, industry and society at the same time in such a way so as to reduce/avoid any negative impact on the environment due to analyses.

The present review article attempts to summarize up-to-date information regarding the green strategies taken up by the workers in this area.

Green strategies :

Prevention is better than cleaning up created waste. So green strategies include atom economy where chemical procedures are designed in a fashion that facilitates the incorporation of maximum of all materials in the final product leading to minimum or zero waste. Analytical schemes are planned in a way that utilizes safer chemicals and generates byproducts with little or no toxicity. Use of safer solvents in minimal volumes is another step towards greening efforts. Other green approach is to achieve energy efficiency which leads to conduct experiments in ambient temperature and pressure along with the use of renewable feedstock. Reducing the amount of solvent drastically makes the process green. Elimination of the solvent altogether is even a better approach i.e. either solventless schemes or direct analysis of samples can be carried out. Avoidance of unnecessary derivatization, use of selective catalysts, design for end product degradation, real-time, in-line monitoring along with waste treatment are some of the green strategies considered so far⁷.

National Environmental Methods Index :

National Environmental Methods Index (NEMI) is a free⁹ searchable online database containing information over 800 regulatory and non-regulatory methods that define, identify, and promote analytical chemistry that use fewer harmful solvents, use safer chemicals, and minimize waste. NEMI has been initiated by the American Chemical Society's Green Chemistry Institute. According to NEMI greening of an analytical method depends on four criteria. A method is defined as less green if :

- (i) PBT – A chemical used in the method is listed as persistent, bioaccumulative, and toxic (PBT), as defined by the EPA's Toxic Release Inventory (TRI)¹⁰.
- (ii) Hazardous – A chemical used in the method is listed

on the TRI or on one of the RCRA's D, F, P or U hazardous waste lists¹¹.

- (iii) Corrosive – pH during the analysis is less than 2 or greater than 12.

- (iv) Waste – Waste amount generated is greater than 50 g.

The greenness of a method is relative and the line between "less green" and "green" is set by the acceptance criteria given above. Using this greenness profile over two-thirds of the methods in NEMI could be evaluated for greenness. The rest could not be evaluated due to the lack of information on sample size, chemicals used, non availability of full method etc.

It is not always possible to use the greenest methods but the greenness profile in the NEMI database can guide us to develop "greener" methods. This article attempts a discussion on some such methods starting from sample pretreatment to waste detoxification via direct measurement and solvent elimination methodologies.

Green pretreatment strategies :

Sample preparation is the bottleneck of analytical methodologies with conventional high reagent consumption, large-scale and labour-intensive procedures. Scientists have developed a variety of green strategies for sample pretreatment. Supercritical fluid extraction, ultrasonic leaching, microwave-assisted extraction, pressurized liquid extraction, ionic liquid extraction, micelle-mediated extraction, solid phase extraction are a few popularly used green technologies.

Supercritical fluid extraction :

Since its extensive development in the early 1980s, supercritical fluid extraction (SFE) has attracted considerable attention as a sample-preparation procedure, SFE uses solvents that are non-toxic, and available at high purity at relatively low cost. It has been found that SFE can extract organic pollutants quantitatively from environmental solids in a short time. CO₂ is one of the most popular fluids used in SFE due to its readily accessible critical parameters ($T_c = 31.1\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; $P_c = 74.8\text{ atm}$).

Supercritical carbon dioxide (SC CO₂) has been used in the extraction of heavy metal ions from their oxides with assistance of ligands and with or without a co-solvent¹². The work involves direct extraction of metal ions from their oxides using neodymium as candidate metal

utilizing a synergy of thenoyl trifluoroacetone (TTA) and tributyl phosphate (TBP). By the reaction with carbonic acid, the metal oxide is converted into metal cation. SC CO₂ facilitates tautomerisation and dissolution of TTA required for the chelation. Addition of methanol to SC CO₂ enhances the formation of metal complex which is being extracted in the SC fluid phase.

Applicability of supercritical carbon dioxide has been increased by using modifiers like compressed propane¹³. The results indicate that solvent and density were important variables in case of CO₂ extraction, whereas in case of propane temperature is the most important variable. The extraction of sesame seed oil with propane was much faster than that with carbon dioxide due to the fact that propane is a better solvent for vegetable oils compared to carbon dioxide.

The first time¹⁴ SFE has been applied to isolate an antimicrobial agent from biological fluids is the case of quantification of orbifloxacin from plasma and milk. Four parameters, including the temperature and the pressure of supercritical fluid, modifier ratios, and dynamic extraction time, were evaluated and optimized to obtain the best yield of the analyte from the biological fluids.

Supercritical fluid extraction has been used for the determination of paraben preservatives and polyphenolic antioxidants in cosmetics¹⁵. The preservatives and antioxidants were extracted from the cosmetic matrices with supercritical carbon dioxide at a pressure of 13,840 kPa at 55 °C for 10 min of static extraction followed by 15 min of dynamic extraction. This method was successfully utilized to determine the amounts of preservatives and antioxidants in real cosmetics without the need for tedious pretreatments.

Bioactive betulonic, betulonic, oleanolic and ursolic acids (triterpenic (TT) acids) were extracted using supercritical fluid extraction method¹⁶. SFE was carried with carbon dioxide at 100, 140 and 200 bar, and 40, 50 and 60 °C, and the extracts were analyzed by GC-MS. Modeling calculations were done for interpreting the SFE results. These results interpret and justify the trends of experimental SFE results.

Ultrasound-assisted extraction :

Ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE) is one of the

techniques promising to speed up and to simplify sample treatment and can be employed for extracting analytes from solid matrices, so that species may then be measured by other instrumental techniques. This technique is regarded as environmentally friendly because in addition to decreased amount of solvent (100–300 mL) and shortened extraction time (3 min⁻¹ h) it can be applied for environmental remediation also.

For the simultaneous determination of flavoring compounds containing safrole, coumarin, 6-methylcoumarin, 7-methoxycoumarin, estragole, methyleugenol, pulegone and thujone, in tobacco additives a new method of UAE followed by dispersive liquid liquid microextraction (DLLME) has been developed¹⁷. This was successfully applied for preconcentration of these target compounds in tobacco additives. Under optimum conditions, the enrichment factors ranges are 140–208. The linear relationship showed satisfactory linearity with correlation coefficients (r^2) over 0.9989 for all the analytes. The limits of detection were between 0.04 and 0.24 ng mL⁻¹ and the average recoveries were between 89.9 and 99.7% (RSDs 2.5–6.7%) in all cases.

Extraction of essential compounds from plants and flowers (viz. laurel, rosemary, thyme, oregano and tuberos) was subjected to the action of an ultrasound probe thus reducing sample amount and avoiding overpressure¹⁸. Kinetic studies show that 10 min is sufficient for extraction and it greatly surpass those provided by steam distillation for essential oils or superheated liquid extraction for these oils and other valuable compounds that too at low cost and high extraction quality.

A rapid, reproducible and simple extraction of the majority capsaicinoids viz. nordihydrocapsaicin, capsaicin, dihydrocapsaicin, homocapsaicin and homodihydrocapsaicin present in hot peppers has been carried out by the employment of ultrasound-assisted extraction¹⁹. Methanol was employed as solvent at a temperature of 50 °C and an extraction time of 10 min for the quantification of the various capsaicinoids present in different varieties of hot peppers cultivated in Spain.

Ultrasound-assisted extraction was employed as a sample preparation method²⁰ prior to the determination of rare earth elements (REEs), i.e. Y, La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd, Tb, Dy, Ho, Er, Tm, Yb and Lu in marine

biological tissues. Diluted single acids (HNO₃ and HCl) and mixtures (HNO₃ and HCl) were evaluated for improving the extraction efficiency. Quantitative recoveries for REEs were achieved using 5 mL of 3% (v/v) HNO₃ and 2% (v/v) HCl, particle size < 200 μm, 3 min of sonication time and 50% of sonication amplitude. Precision, expressed as relative standard deviation from three independent extractions, ranged from 0.1 to 8%.

For the determination of ultra trace levels of gold in water samples, soils and river sediments a combination of ultrasound-assisted extraction²¹ and dispersive liquid-liquid microextraction was used. Since an HCl medium was required for the formation of the AuCl₄⁻ complex, HCl together with HNO₃ was used as extractants for ultrasound-assisted extraction. The enrichment factor obtained was 220 for water samples. Moreover, the extraction efficiency was around 96%.

Microwave assisted extraction :

Microwave assisted extraction (MAE) is one of the milestones in the development of sample preparation strategies. It has a broad applicability and extractions can be easily carried out from difficult sample matrices. From the viewpoint of green chemistry the advantages of MAE are significant reduction of solvent amount (25–50 mL) which in turn reduces waste generation leading to shortening of extraction time (3 min⁻¹ h) with reduction of sample quantity and correspondingly reduced energy input and cost.

Avermectines (abamectine, doramectine and ivermectine) in soils have been extracted with acetonitrile/water (90 : 10) by using microwave assisted extraction²². Soil physico-chemical properties and aging influence extraction.

Ultrasonic/microwave assisted extraction (UMAE) method was developed for efficient sample pretreatment of flavonoids in *Spatholobus suberectus* for rapid characterization²³. The optimal conditions were microwave power of 300 W, extraction time of 450 s, 70% methanol as extraction solvent, solvent to solid ratio of 20 mL/g, ultrasound power of 50 W, extraction temperature of 80 °C, and one extraction cycle. Compared with commonly used extraction methods, UMAE showed higher efficiency and shorter extraction time for sample preparation.

For the extraction of flavone and coumarin compounds from medicinal plants microwave-assisted extraction was employed²⁴. The conditions of MAE including the size of sample, liquid/solid ratio, extraction temperature and extraction time were optimized by means of an orthogonal design L9 (3⁴). In this work aqueous solution of polyethylene glycol (PEG) was employed for the first time as a green solvent in microwave assisted extraction of flavone and coumarin compounds.

For the speciation analysis of arsenic in edible oil extraction of arsenic species, microwave-assisted extraction method was used²⁵. For speciation the arsenic species studied include arsenite, arsenate, monomethylarsonic acid, dimethylarsinic acid, arsenobetaine and arsenocholine. The concentrations of arsenic species have been determined in several used and fresh vegetable oil samples. The extraction efficiency was better than 92%.

For the determination of 40 currently used pesticides (CUPs) in airborne particulate matter (PM₁₀) at trace level microwave assisted extraction method was used²⁶. This was followed by a gel permeation chromatography (GPC) clean-up and determination by GC-MS/MS.

Pressurized liquid extraction :

Pressurized liquid extraction (PLE) technique is a fast process using much less solvent (10–40 mL) compared to conventional procedures at elevated pressures (10–14 MPa) and temperatures (50–200 °C). Solvent consumption is reduced as a result of the higher analyte solubility at elevated temperatures. Reduction in the use of solvents, shorter analysis time and less energy consumption are some of the green aspects of PLE.

To develop an efficient green extraction approach for recovery of bioactive compounds from natural plants, the potential of pressurized liquid extraction (PLE) of ginger (*Zingiber officinale* Roscoe) with bioethanol/water as solvents was examined²⁷. PLE with 70% bioethanol operated at 1500 psi and 100 °C for 20 min (static extraction time : 5 min) was recommended as optimized extraction conditions, achieving 106.8%, 109.3% and 108.0% yield of [6]-, [8]- and [10]-gingerol relative to the yield of corresponding constituent obtained by 8 h Soxhlet extraction (absolute ethanol as extraction solvent).

Simultaneous extraction of arsenic and selenium species viz. As^{III}, As^V, Se^{IV} and Se^{VI} in atmospheric par-

ticulate matter (PM₁₀) was carried out using a chelating solvent-based pressurized liquid extraction method²⁸. Out of the several chelating solvents used the best results were obtained with EDTA.

Sewage sludge is often regarded as one of the worst environmental matrices to extract as it can contain high concentrations of organic chemicals and their degradation products as well as high amounts of organic matter. Extraction conditions were carefully selected to achieve maximal recovery of PAHs contained in sewage sludge while eliminating most of the interfering matrix components²⁹. This new sample preparation procedure consists of on-line clean-up by inclusion of sorbents in the extraction cell, and combines elevated temperatures and pressures with liquid solvents to achieve fast and efficient removal of target analytes from complex sewage sludge matrices. The best results were obtained when selective pressurized liquid extraction (SPLE) conditions were fixed at specified condition : 140 °C, 1500 psi, static time of 5 min and *n*-hexane as extraction solvent.

Three pyrethroid, one carbamate and two organophosphorus pesticides were extracted by pressurized liquid extraction from edible seaweeds with integrated clean-up, followed by gas chromatography coupled to tandem mass spectrometry³⁰. Five PLE parameters were investigated using a screening design : temperature, static extraction time, number of cycles, percent of flush volume and quantitative composition of the *n*-hexane/ethyl acetate extraction solvent. Recoveries in real seaweed samples were within the range 82–108%.

The effect of extraction temperature (150, 175 and 200 °C) on the simultaneous PLE of polychlorinated dibenzo-*p*-dioxins (PCDDs), polychlorinated dibenzofurans (PCDFs), and dioxin-like polychlorinated biphenyls (DL-PCBs) from a sediment sample (certified reference material : JSAC 0431) using polar and nonpolar solvents were studied³¹. To determine the optimum conditions for PLE, six single solvents (toluene, dichloromethane, benzene, acetonitrile, acetone and methanol) were used as extractants. The efficiency of PLE for 2,3,7,8-substituted PCDDs, 2,3,7,8-substituted PCDFs, and DL-PCBs, as obtained by PLE using the solvents toluene, dichloromethane, benzene, and acetonitrile, showed an increase with increasing extraction temperature.

Pressurized Hot Water Extraction (PHWE) is a subclass of PLE, where the solvent is mainly water. The term "pressurized hot water" is used to denote the region of condensed phase of water between the temperatures 100 °C (boiling point of water) to 374 °C (critical temperature of water). Other common terms such as "superheated water", "near critical water", "subcritical water", "high temperature extraction" and "extraction using hot compressed water" have also been used. Due to the replacement of organic solvents, pressurized hot water extraction has become a popular green extraction method for different classes of compounds present in numerous kinds of matrices such as environmental, food and botanical samples. The main parameters which influence its extraction efficiency are namely the temperature, extraction time, flow rates and addition of modifiers/additives.

Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) in sewage sludge were extracted using pressurized hot water extraction³². The PHWE was optimized with regard to the pH of solvent as well as other operational parameters. The optimum conditions were 0.01 *M* NaOH as the extraction solvent, temperature of 120 °C, pressure of 100 bar, static time 5 min, 5 cycles, flush volume 90% and purge time 60 s.

Subcritical water can be an excellent alternative to organic solvents as a medium for extracting flavonol quercetin, due to its temperature-dependent selectivity, safety, efficiency of recovery and lower cost. In the study of subcritical water extraction (SWE) of quercetin from onion skin³³ the maximum yield of quercetin (16.29 ± 0.75 mg/g onion skin) was obtained at extraction temperature of 165 °C, extraction time of 15 min, mixture ratio of 1.5 : 2.5 for onion skin and diatomaceous earth (DE).

Potato peel waste is a disposal problem but, it is a good source of functional ingredients such as phenolic compounds. The study of Pal Singh and Saldana³⁴ investigated the extraction of eight phenolic compounds (gallic acid, GAC; chlorogenic acid, CGA; caffeic acid, CFA; protocatechuic acid, PCA; syringic acid, SGA; *p*-hydroxyl benzoic acid, PBA; ferulic acid, FRA and coumaric acid, CMA) from potato peel using subcritical water. It was found that subcritical water at 160 to 180 °C, 6 MPa and 60 min might be a good substitute to organic solvents such as methanol and ethanol to obtain phenolic com-

pounds from potato peel.

Ionic liquid extraction :

Ionic liquids (ILs) are eutectic molten salts consisting of bulky asymmetry organic cation and either organic or inorganic anion whose melting point is below 100 °C. Their unique properties such as negligible volatility, thermal stability and non-flammability have been accepted as a new green solvent. ILs have found uses in different sub-disciplines of analytical chemistry. Due to eco-friendly behaviour, they have been increasingly investigated worldwide as alternative reaction media to replace traditional organic solvents.

The use of 8-sulfonamidoquinoline derivatives as chelate extraction reagents for solvent extraction of several divalent metal cations using an ionic liquid, 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium hexafluorophosphate ([BMIM][PF₆]) as extraction phase was investigated as novel extraction reagents for ionic liquid extraction system³⁵. The studied reagents could be used as extractants for the metal cations in the [BMIM][PF₆] extraction system which were superior to that in chloroform system. Use of the derivative having trifluoromethyl group, Cd^{II} was extracted as anionic complex while others as hydrate complex.

In the study of Ying *et al.*³⁶, 1-butyl-3-methylimidazoliumhexafluorophosphate ([C₄MIM][PF₆]) was used to preconcentrate chromium species. The simultaneous preconcentration of Cr^{VI} and Cr^{III} in wastewater was achieved with ammonium pyrrolidinedithiocarbamate (APDC) as the chelating agent and the ionic liquid [C₄MIM][PF₆] as the extractant. Common metal ions in water did not interfere with the determination.

The optimum conditions for the extraction of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Pb^{II} in water by liquid-liquid extraction method were investigated using the synthetic ionic liquid 1-butyl-3-methylimidazoliumhexafluorophosphate, [BMIM] [PF₆] combined with 2-aminothiophenol ligand³⁷. The results showed that the optimum pH for the extraction of Ni^{II} and Pb^{II} was 4–6 and 5, respectively whereas the extraction of Cu^{II} was independent of the pH of solution. The extraction equilibria of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Pb^{II} were reached within 120, 30 and 30 min, respectively. Na^I, Ca^{II}, Mg^{II}, SO₄²⁻ and Cl⁻ ions did not show significant interference in the extraction efficiency of the heavy metal ions. The extraction efficiency of all metal ions with the ligand in

the ionic liquid was higher than that obtained in chloroform using the same conditions.

For the first time ionic liquid was employed for selective isolation of heme-protein species³⁸. Ionic liquid 1-butyl-3-trimethylsilylimidazolium hexafluorophosphate [BTMSIM][PF₆] quantitatively extracted hemoglobin at the level of 100 ng μL⁻¹ in the absence of any co-existing extractants/additives at pH 7. Other protein species do not interfere and remain in the aqueous phase. The present system was applied for selective isolation of heme-protein, i.e. hemoglobin from human whole blood without any pretreatment, giving rise to satisfactory results.

As the first attempt, ionic liquid solutions have been employed for direct extraction of proteins from yeast cells³⁹. Compared with effects of 21 different ionic liquid solutions on the extraction efficiency, 3-(dimethylamino)-1-propylammonium formate ([DMAPA][FA]) was found to be the suitable ionic liquid solution. Results indicated that the chemical properties of target proteins remained unchanged during the extraction process and maintained their immunoreactivity and biological functions.

Micelle mediated extraction :

Micelle mediated extraction (MME) technique has been utilized for extraction, purification, separation and preconcentration of metal chelates, organic compounds, and proteins. This is due to the fact that aqueous solutions of certain surfactant micelles exhibit phase separation behavior upon temperature alteration. The surfactant is a non-volatile, non-flammable, non-toxic and safe sorbent and is used as a diluted solution. Since the addition of just a small amount of an appropriate nonionic or zwitterionic surfactant to the aqueous sample solution is required, this approach is convenient and fairly benign, eliminating the need for the use of organic solvents as in conventional extraction method.

A simple mixed-micelle cloud point extraction procedure for speciation analysis of chromium⁴⁰ in water samples was developed by electrothermal atomic absorption spectrometry. A mixed micelle consisting of sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) and Triton X-114 was used as an extracting agent. Cr^{VI} was complexed with 1,5-diphenyl carbazide (OPC) in an HCl medium and it was concentrated in the surfactant rich phase after phase separation. Total chromium was extracted after oxidation. Cr^{III} was

calculated from the difference. The main factors influencing the mixed-micelle cloud point extraction are concentration of HCl, DPC, SDS and Triton X-114, equilibrium temperature and incubation time.

For simultaneous preconcentration and determination of trace amounts of U^{VI} , Th^{IV} , Zr^{IV} and Hf^{IV} ions in aqueous samples micelle mediated extraction was carried out⁴¹. The metal ions in 0.1 M sodium acetate solution formed complexes with dibenzoyl methane (DBM) followed by Triton X-114 (0.2%, w/v). Phase separation occurred at 50 °C.

Use of micelle-mediated extraction (MME) of anthraquinones from the root of *Morinda citrifolia* and cloud point concentration (CPC) of the extract as effective alternatives for extraction and concentration of the product without using toxic organic solvent was investigated⁴². To determine the effect of concentrations on the percent anthraquinones extracted two types of surfactants : Triton X-100 and Genapol X-080 were used at ambient pressure and temperature. The result showed a lower temperature requirement reducing compound degradation along with reduction of the amount of energy and concentration of the analyte. This was used to quantify the amount of the most medicinally important anti-cancer compound, damnacanthal.

The first report of simultaneous analysis of vanadium and molybdenum in foodstuff samples describes a micelle-mediated extraction method for preconcentration of trace quantities of V^V and Mo^{VI} as a prior step to their simultaneous spectrophotometric determination⁴³. Bromopyrogallol red, cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) (cationic surfactant) and KI were used as chelating, extraction and co-extraction agents, respectively. The method was applied to the simultaneous determination of V^V and Mo^{VI} in several plant foodstuff samples successfully.

The phase-separation phenomenon of non-ionic surfactants occurring in aqueous solution was used for the extraction of Pb^{II} from digested blood samples after simultaneous complexation with ammonium pyrrolidinedithiocarbamate (APDC) and diethyldithiocarbamate (DDTC) separately⁴⁴. The complexed analyte was quantitatively extracted with octylphenoxypolyethoxyethanol (Triton X-114). The proposed method was used for de-

termination of Pb^{II} in blood samples of children with kidney disorders and healthy controls.

Solid phase extraction :

Solid-phase extraction (SPE) is currently the most frequently employed technique for isolating or enriching analytes from various samples. Liquid-solid extractions provide the opportunity to eliminate solvents in the pre-treatment process because the analyte can be directly extracted from the liquid sample onto the solid sorbent material. A wide variety of sorbents are available with more being developed by the chemists.

Chemically modified fly ash from coal-fired power station was used as a sorbent for the removal of fluoride from drinking water⁴⁵. Two types of beds were used. Fly ash was treated with 12 M HCl followed by neutralization with NaOH to obtain Bed I. Bed II was obtained by modifying Bed I with ferric alum and magnesium chloride. Adsorption of fluoride occurs best at pH 4–6 on Bed II. The residual fluoride in the effluent is much below the WHO permissible limit for drinking water. Raw materials are available free of cost. It was found that the total expenditure for the production of modified fly ash would be ₹ 9/- per kg.

Polystyrene-divinylbenzene functionalized with xanthine was used as a sorbent for separation of Ni^{2+} and Cd^{2+} ions⁴⁶. pH 1 was the optimum pH for both the metal ions whereas 1 M sulphosalicylic acid and 10% thiourea in 0.1 M $HClO_4$ were the specific eluting agents respectively. Exchange capacities of Ni^{II} and Cd^{II} were found to be 0.57 mmol g^{-1} and 0.73 mmol g^{-1} , respectively. Regeneration and reuse of the resin is possible.

Cation exchange solid phase extraction based on Oasis HLB cartridges was used to concentrate some common pharmaceuticals in fish tissue, reclaimed water, and the surface water directly affected by irrigation with reclaimed water⁴⁷. The pharmaceuticals were analyzed by liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry. Bioaccumulation factors were calculated and this is the first report of potential accumulation of caffeine in fish from a water body directly influenced by reclaimed water.

The first study on the high efficiency of nanometer-sized γ -alumina coated with sodium dodecyl sulfate-1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-naphthol (SDS-PAN) as a new sorbent in

solid phase extraction has been reported by Ezoddin *et al.*⁴⁸. A microcolumn packed with modified nanometer-sized alumina was used to preconcentrate and separate Cd and Pb in water and herbal samples. Under the optimized operating conditions, the sorption capacities of the modified nano- γ -alumina for Cd and Pb were 11.1 and 16.4 mg g⁻¹ respectively.

A simple and sensitive porous polypropylene membrane-protected micro-solid-phase extraction (μ -SPE) approach for the sample preparation and determination of carbamate pesticides in soil samples has been described⁴⁹. The μ -SPE device consisted of C18 sorbent held within a porous polypropylene envelope. The extraction efficiency

of the μ -SPE was very high, with detection limits in the range of 0.01–0.40 ng g⁻¹ which is more than two orders of magnitude lower than the limits obtained by the United States Environmental Protection Agency Methods 8321A and 8318. The reproducibility of separate μ -SPE device used for experiments was satisfactory indicating that the method is reliable for routine environmental analysis.

Table 1 gives a compact presentation of the green strategies of sample pretreatment of various matrices for the detection of the environmentally significant analytes. Some of the interesting observations can be cited here. Supercritical fluid extraction has been established as the extractant for not only organics but also inorganic metal

Table 1. Typical examples of green strategies for sample pretreatment

Green strategy	Matrix	Analyte	Method	Ref.
SFE	Metal oxide	Nd ^{III}	Direct <i>in situ</i> SFE using thenoyltrifluoroacetone-tributylphosphate-methanol in carbon dioxide	12
SFE	Sesame seed	Sesame seed oil	Supercritical carbon dioxide and compressed propane were used as solvents followed by DSC-GC determination	13
SFE	Plasma and milk	Orbifloxacin	Determinations were carried out using HPLC-FLD	14
SFE	Cosmetics	Paraben preservatives and polyphenolic antioxidants	SFE <i>in situ</i> derivatization and polyphenolic on-line HS-SPME-GC-MS	15
SFE	<i>Eucalyptus globulus</i> bark	Bioactive triterpenic acids	SC CO ₂ followed by GC-MS	16
UAE	Tobacco additives	Safrole, coumarin, 6-methylcoumarin, 7-methoxycoumarin, estragole, methyleugenol, pulegone and thujone	DAE followed by DLLME	17
UAE	Laurel, rosemary, thyme, oregano and tuberose	Essential oils	Solid sample subjected to the action of an ultrasound probe	18
UAE	Hot peppers	Nordihydrocapsaicin, capsaicin, dihydrocapsaicin, homocapsaicin and homodihydrocapsaicin	Analyzed by HPLC with fluorescence detection and using monolithic columns for the chromatographic separation	19
UAE	Marine biological tissues	Y, La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd, Tb, Dy, Ho, Er, Tm, Yb and Lu	Determination by UAE-tissues ICP-MS	20
UAE	Water, soil and river sediment	Ultratrace levels of gold	Combination of UAE and dispersive liquid-liquid microextraction with final detection by ETAAS	21
MAE	Soil	Abamectine, doramectine and ivermectine	Analyzed by UHPLC-MS/MS	22
MAE	Spatholobus suberectus herb	Flavonoids	UMAE-diagnostic ion filtering strategy – LC-Q-TOF-MS	23

Table-1 (contd.)

MAE	Lysionotus pauciflorus and <i>Cortex fraxini</i>	Nevadensin and aesculin and aesculetin	PEG-MAE	24
MAE	Edible oil	Arsenite, arsenate, monomethyl arsonic acid, dimethylarsinic acid, arsenobetaine and arsenocholine	IC combined with ICP-MS	25
MAE	Airborne particulate matter (PM ₁₀)	40 currently used pesticides	MAE-gel permeation chromatography clean-up and determination by GC-MS/MS	26
PLE	Ginger	[6]-, [8]- and [10]-gingerol	PLE with bioethanol or water	27
PLE	Atmospheric particulate matter (PM ₁₀)	As ^{III} , As ^V , Se ^{IV} and Se ^{VI}	Evaluated by HPLC-HG-AFS	28
PLE	Sewage sludge	Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs)	Programmed temperature vaporization-gas chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry method (PTV-LVI-GC-MS/MS)	29
PLE	Edible seaweeds	Pyrethroid, carbamate and organophosphorus pesticides	PLE-PTV-LVI-GC MS/MS	30
PLE	Sediment	Polychlorinated dibenzo- <i>p</i> -dioxins (PCDDs), polychlorinated dibenzofurans (PCDFs), and dioxin-like polychlorinated biphenyls (DL-PCBs)	PLE using toluene, dichloromethane, benzene, acetonitrile, acetone, and methanol	31
PHWE	Sewage sludge	Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs)	PHWE-purified and preconcentrated by three-phase hollow fiber liquid phase microextraction (HF-LPME) followed by LC-ESI-MS analysis	32
SWE	Onion skin	Flavonol quercetin	Subcritical water extraction	33
SWE	Potato peel	Gallic acid, chlorogenic acid, caffeic acid, protocatechuic acid, syringic acid, <i>p</i> -hydroxyl benzoic acid, ferulic acid, and coumaric acid	Subcritical water extraction	34
ILE	Metal ions	Bivalent metal cations	8-Sulfonamidoquinoline derivatives as chelate with [BMIM][PF ₆] as extraction phase	35
ILE	Wastewater	Cr ^{VI} and Cr ^{III}	APDC as the chelating agent and the ionic liquid [C ₄ MIM][PF ₆] as the extractant – HPLC	36
ILE	Water	Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} and Pb ^{II}	Ionic liquid combined with 2-aminothiophenol ligand-liquid-liquid extraction method	37
ILE	Human blood	Hemoglobin	[BTMSIM][PF ₆]- ⁵⁷ Fe Mössbauer spectra and circular dichroism (CD) spectra	38
ILE	Yeast cells	Proteins	[DMAPA]FA-sodium dodecyl sulfate-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE) and 2-dimensional gel electrophoresis (2-DE) were employed for separation	39
MME	Water	Cr ^{VI} and Cr ^{III}	Mixed micelle consisting of sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) and Triton X-114 as an extracting agent – ET-AAS	40
MME	Aqueous samples	U ^{VI} , Th ^{IV} , Zr ^{IV} and Hf ^{IV}	0.1 M sodium acetate-dibenzoylmethane-Triton X-114 mixed micelle – ICP-OES	41
MME	Root of <i>Morinda citrifolia</i>	Medicinally important anti-cancer compound, damnacanthol	Micelle-mediated pressurized hot water extraction – HPLC	42

Table-1 (contd.)

MME	Foodstuff	V ^V and Mo ^{VI}	Bromopyrogallol red, cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (cationic surfactant) and KI as chelating, extraction and co-extraction agents, respectively – spectrophotometric determination	43
MME	Blood	Pb ^{II}	Simultaneous complexation with ammonium pyrrolidinedithiocarbamate and diethyldithiocarbamate – extracted with Triton X-114-FAAS	44
SPE	Drinking water	Fluoride	Modified flyash sorbent – UV-Vis	45
SPE	Natural water	Ni ^{II} and Cd ^{II}	Xanthine functionalized PS-DVB resin – FAAS	46
SPE	Fish tissue, reclaimed water, and the surface water directly affected by irrigation with reclaimed water	Trimethoprim, caffeine, sulfamethoxazole, diphenhydramine, diltiazem, carbamazepine, erythromycin, and fluoxetine	Combination of SPE liquid chromatography – tandem mass spectrometry	47
SPE	Water and herbal samples	Cd ^{II} and Pb ^{II}	Nanometer-sized γ -alumina coated with sodium dodecyl sulfate-1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-naphthol (SDS-PAN) as sorbent – FAAS	48
SPE	Soil	Carbamate pesticides	C ₁₈ sorbent held within porous polypropylene membrane – μ -SPE-HPLC	49

ions¹². Ultrasound assisted extraction and microwave assisted extraction can be suitably applied for all kind of hazardous samples including pesticides²⁶, speciation of arsenic²⁵. Pressurized liquid extraction, pressurized hot water extraction and subcritical water extraction are now being coming out as effective extracting agents for varieties of organic compounds^{29,32–34}. Interesting applications of using ionic liquids in the protein analyses^{38,39} and micelle mediated extraction of metal ions in food stuff⁴³ and blood⁴⁴ have been reported. The new direction of application of solid phase extraction includes the analyses of fish tissue, reclaimed water, and the surface water directly affected by irrigation with reclaimed water⁴⁷ and pesticides⁴⁹.

Direct measurement of solid samples :

The trends in new sample-preparation methods that minimize the amount of reagents and organic solvents contribute to improving the environmentally-friendly features of those analytical procedures that cannot be applied directly to samples with no sample treatment (Fig. 2). Nevertheless, when the use of reagents is unavoidable and their substitution is not feasible, the alternative is either elimination or minimization of their consumption. The most direct way for greening analytical methods are

Fig. 2. Spectroscopic methods for direct measurement of solid samples (based on search results at www.sciencedirect.com).

based on the elimination of the sample treatment steps. At this point, direct measurement of solid samples plays an important role in the green chemistry context. Analytical methods based on spectroscopy are amongst those that dominate GAC.

Solid phase spectrophotometry :

The determination of trace metals in solid samples has traditionally been performed by acid digestion and subse-

quent measurement by a suitable instrumental technique. This dissolution step is time-consuming and it shows important drawbacks. For these reasons, in the past years many efforts have been focused on the direct analysis of solid samples. Solid phase spectrophotometry (SPS) is one of them.

A new simple, very sensitive, selective and accurate procedure for the determination of trace amounts of Fe^{II} in tap, mineral and well water samples by solid-phase spectrophotometry⁵⁰ has been developed. The procedure is based on fixation of Fe^{II} as 2,3-dichloro-6-(3-carboxy-2-hydroxy-1-naphthylazo)quinoxaline on a styrene-divinylbenzene anion-exchange resin. The absorbance of resin sorbed Fe^{II} complex is measured directly at 743 and 830 nm. Fe^{III} was determined by difference measurements after reduction of Fe^{III} to Fe^{II} with hydroxylamine hydrochloride.

In this study a novel and very simple microextraction approach for preconcentration and direct solid phase spectrophotometric measurement has been developed for the determination of chromogenic analytes⁵¹. The model analyte to assess this approach was the chromophore malachite green (MG). The analyte was extracted from water samples onto a small rotating disk made of Teflon containing a sorbent phase of polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) on one of its surfaces. It was referred as the rotating disk sorptive extraction (RDSE). After extraction, the sorbent phase with the concentrated analyte was separated from the Teflon disk and used directly for MG determination by solid phase spectrophotometry at 624 nm, without the necessity of a desorption step. The PDMS phases could be reused after desorbing the MG into methanol for 3 h. Replacement of the PDMS film onto the disk is very easy and low cost.

The work of Saavedra *et al.*⁵² determines metal complexes in a solid phase by photoacoustic spectrometry (PAS). The method is based on Co^{II} colorimetric reaction with 3-(2-pyridyl)-5,6-bis(4-sulfophenyl)-1,2,4-triazine (FST, ferrozine) retained on an anion-exchange resin, DEAE Sephadex A-25. The immobilization of Co^{II} on the solid phase is combined with PAS measurement. The Co^{II} concentration in water samples was determined by conventional photoacoustic measurement.

Flow injection solid phase spectrophotometry :

Due to some improvements in flow injection analysis, such as sequential injection and lab-on-a-valve, it is possible not only to reduce the reagent consumption but also to devise fully automatic and miniaturized systems with minimal maintenance needs. This may have the potential of becoming one of the green analytical methods.

The micro-column packed with diphenylcarbazone-functionalized silica gel was used for on-line solid-phase extraction and determination of mercury in real samples by flow-injection spectrophotometry⁵³. The simple, fast, low cost and environment friendly method was used to separate and enrich Hg^{II} selectively from eight metal ions with similar characteristics such as Cd^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Mn^{II}, Pb^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cu^{II} and Fe^{III}.

A simple and robust on-line sequential injection system based on solid phase extraction coupled to a flow injection hydride generation atomic absorption spectrometer (FI-HGAAS) with a heated quartz tube atomizer (QTA) was developed and optimized for the determination of As^{III} in groundwater without any kind of sample pretreatment⁵⁴. The method was based on the selective retention of inorganic As^V that was carried out by passing the filtered original sample through a cartridge containing a chloride-form strong anion exchanger. Thus the most toxic form, inorganic As^{III}, was determined fast and directly by AsH₃ generation. The concentration of As^V was calculated by difference between the total soluble inorganic arsenic and As^{III} concentrations.

A greener analytical procedure⁵⁵ based on flow-injection solid-phase spectrophotometry has been proposed for iron determination. Fe^{II} is reversibly retained on 1-(2-thiazolylazo)-2-naphthol immobilized on C18-bonded silica, yielding a brown complex. The metal ion is eluted as Fe^{II} with a small volume of a diluted acid solution without removing the immobilized reagent, which can be used for at least 100 determinations. The procedure involves a reduced effluent generation (3.6 mL per determination) and consumes micro amounts of reagents.

Solid phase fluorescence :

Solid phase fluorescence (SPF) spectroscopy is a green approach in analytical chemistry. This is a low cost method which does not require sample pretreatment. The method is simple and fast with no waste generation.

The determination of acetylsalicylic acid (ASA), paracetamol and caffeine in pharmaceutical formulations using solid-phase molecular fluorescence was carried out by Alves and Poppi⁵⁶. This methodology is applicable even in the presence of unknown interferences and with spectral overlap of the components in the mixture. A low cost method with no sample preparation, simple and fast analysis using fluorescence spectrometer and no generation of waste, makes this method very attractive, allowing for the simultaneous determination of compounds with good reproducibility and accuracy.

The current methods to characterize solid organic wastes (SOW) are tedious, time-consuming and often insufficiently informative. This study tries to assess the potential of solid-phase fluorescence spectroscopy⁵⁷ to quickly provide a relevant characterization of SOW. For SOW samples, three dimensional solid-phase fluorescence (3D-SPF) spectra were successfully recorded for municipal solid waste (MSW) and most of its sub-components (foods, cardboard) but impossible for sewage sludge (SS), sludge compost (SC) and ligno-cellulosic wastes. It was concluded that the presence of highly light-absorptive chemical structures in such dark-colored samples was responsible for this limitation. For characterization of such samples, i.e. lignin, humic acid, SS, SC and ligno-cellulosic wastes, laser induced fluorescence (LIF) spectroscopy enables the acquisition of 20 fluorescence spectra.

The eggshell membrane (ESM) contains several surface functional groups such as amines, amides and carboxylic groups with potential as SPE adsorbent⁵⁸. A typical biomaterial, ESM was used as a solid-phase extraction (SPE) adsorbent for analysis of trace As^V in natural water samples in combination with hydride generation atomic fluorescence spectrometry (HG-AFS).

Solid sampling electrothermal atomic absorption spectrometry :

Electrothermal atomic absorption spectrometry (ETAAS) is one of the most widely used methods for trace analysis of solid materials. However, the unavoidable sample digestion in the conventional working mode leads to a serious worsening of the instrumental performance of this method and also affects the environment. Therefore, digestion-free sampling techniques including slurry sampling (SIS-ETAAS) and direct solid sampling

(SS-ETAAS) have gained great importance.

The lead concentrations of chewing gum samples⁵⁹ having different compositions were determined by solid sampling ETAAS. The samples were ashed at 400 °C for 2 h prior to direct determination by SS-ETAAS applying 600 °C of pyrolysis and 1600 °C of atomization temperatures without adding a modifier, acid and/or surfactant. The technique was fast, simple and the risks of contamination and analyte loss were low.

Cadmium, chromium, lead and antimony were determined in slurries prepared using pulverized samples of personal computers and mobile phones dispersed in dimethylformamide medium⁶⁰. Determinations were carried out by ETAAS using a graphite furnace. The pyrolysis temperatures were fixed at 600 °C (for Cd), 700 °C (for Pb), 1100 °C (for Sb), and 1200 °C (for Cr); atomization temperatures were established as 1400 °C (for Cd), 1300 °C (for Pb), 1900 °C (for Sb), and 2300 °C (for Cr), and the chemical modifier 50 µg NH₄H₂PO₄ + 3 µg Mg(NO₃)₂ was used for Cd and Pb while 5 µg Pd + 3 µg Mg(NO₃)₂ was used for Sb. The use of a chemical modifier for Cr determination was not necessary.

A simple and rapid method for the direct determination by SS-ETAAS of Cd, Cr, Cu, Pb and Zn in soil was developed⁶¹ using three certified reference materials of soil : Eutric Cambisol, Orthic Luvisols and Rendzina, which differed in their matrix composition. Chemical modifiers were essential to achieve reproducible and interference-free signals for the analytes studied. The best results were obtained with a Pd/Mg(NO₃)₂ admixture for the determination of Cd, Pb and Zn and NH₄F for Cu. The combination of W (as a permanent modifier) and Mg(NO₃)₂ provided well-defined signal profiles for Cr. Under optimized conditions, the analyte and matrix were separated effectively *in situ*.

Solvent elimination methodology :

Solvent elimination methodology is an effective green strategy to overcome the use of toxic organic solvents used in conventional methods in large excess. Solid phase extraction (SPE), microwave hydrodiffusion and gravity extraction (MHO), use of green solvents and reagents are green strategies that effectively eliminate toxic solvents and reagents in existing analytical procedures. Fig. 3 gives

Fig. 3. Solvent elimination methodologies (based on search results at www.sciencedirect.com).

us an idea of the strategies used in greening the processes.

Solid-phase microextraction (SPME) was developed in 1990s. It not only enhances the extraction efficiencies compared to traditional solid-phase extraction (SPE) but also conforms to the requirements of GAC. It can eliminate or reduce toxic reagents and minimize analytical wastes that are hazardous to health and environment. The preservatives and antioxidants were extracted from the cosmetic matrices with SC CO₂¹⁵. The extractant subsequently was derivatized *in situ* with the silylation reagent N,O-bis(trimethylsilyl)trifluoroacetamide with 0.1% trimethylchlorosilane. The product was then adsorbed on a polyacrylate solid-phase microextraction (SPME) fiber in the headspace. Better results were obtained by combining SPME and SFE methods. The detection limits ranged from 0.5 to 8.3 mg g⁻¹.

Divinyl-benzene/carboxen/polydimethylsiloxane (DVB/CAR/PDMS) SPME fibre was used for multi-elemental speciation of organometallic compounds of mercury, lead and tin in water samples combined with gas chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry method as detection technique⁶². The combination of both techniques HS-SPME and GC-MS/MS allowed attaining lower limits of detection (4–33 ng L⁻¹).

Of the seven SPME fibers used 65 μm polydimethylsiloxane/divinylbenzene (PDMS/DVB) was the most suitable fiber type for the extraction of compounds originating from particles of unburned propellant powders or

organic gunshot residues (OGSR) viz. diphenylamine (DPA), 4-nitrodiphenylamine (4-NDPA), ethyl centralite (EC), nitroglycerin (NG) and dibutyl phthalate (DBP)⁶³. Extracts were analysed by gas chromatography/mass spectrometry (GC/MS). Optimal extraction time parameter was found to be 35 min.

Biosorption has recently received a great deal of attention due to low costs of the materials used and for their environmentally friendly nature. Chitosan a hetero polymer constituted by glucosamine and a fraction of acetylglucosamine residues is a well known biopolymer characterized by its high sorption capacity. Two chitosan derivatives⁶⁴ were used as solid phase extractors for several radionuclides viz. ¹³⁷Cs, ^{85,89}Sr, ¹⁵²Eu, ²⁴¹Am, ²³⁴Th and ²³³U. 1.9 mL sample volume was used for extraction of the nucleids. Na₂CO₃ was the best eluant for U whereas EDTA was for Th. Miniaturization is applied in not only sample preparation but also in analytical instruments used in the final determination of analytes.

Miniaturization is primarily aimed to reduce costs which in turn automatically reduce consumption of reagents, decreasing analysis times and sample volumes, increasing separation efficiency and enabling automation. Analytical techniques such as flow-injection analysis (FIA) reduce the solvent and reagent consumption thus greening the analytical methods. Flow-injection solid-phase coupled with spectrophotometry has been used for Hg^{II} and Fe^{II} determinations^{53,55} and flow injection hydride generation atomic absorption spectrometry⁵⁴ has been used for the speciation of As. Minimization of solvent volume justifies using this analytical method as green strategy.

An innovative solvent free⁶⁵ microwave hydrodiffusion and gravity extraction (MHG) of flavonol content from onion (*Allium cepa* L.) was studied. The extraction of total phenolic content has been effectively evaluated and compared with conventional solvent extraction. Microwave extraction offered important advantages like shorter extraction time (23 min), a green strategy with no solvent or water used and extraction of valuable onion crude juice retaining fresh organoleptic properties with higher phenolic content at optimized power (500 W). Microwave extraction resulted significant yield (81.5%) with 41.9% of flavonol contents, with better retain of remaining flavonoids (55.9%) in residues of onions. Polyethylene gly-

col (PEG) was employed for the first time as a green solvent in the extraction of flavone and coumarin compounds. CO₂ and water are also used as green solvents in case of SFE¹²⁻¹⁶ and PHWE, SWE³²⁻³⁴ respectively.

An alkaloid piperine and a protein arachin were isolated from black pepper and groundnut respectively and used as bioreagents⁶⁶ which are selective and specific for gold and mercury. This study shows that bioreagents have the potential to replace toxic and hazardous chemicals and used as green reagents.

The simple extracts from some available local plants including butterfly pea flower, orchid flower, and beet root were found to be useful as alternative self indicator reagents for acidity assay. Various tea drinks were explored to be used for chromogenic reagents in iron determination. The combination of natural reagents with minimal processed extracts and the low volume requirement flow based systems helped to create some unique green chemical analyses⁶⁷.

An easy, cheap and green synthetic route, using high-power ultrasounds and sodium citrate dihydrate as non-toxic reducing and stabilizer agent, produces gold nanoparticles in aqueous solution with half-life more than 30 days, at ambient conditions. The time required for the synthesis is 5.5 min⁶⁸. The resources can be optimized at low cost, with low time of synthesis and no waste production.

Waste treatment :

Concern about environmental protection has increased over the years from a global viewpoint⁶⁹. The generation of hazardous wastes (chemical by-products) is a threat to our environment. Green strategies are being applied more and more to overcome this problem. It designs analytical methods in such a way so as to generate minimum amount of waste. Detoxification of produced waste is carried out by bioremediation, green removal of toxic metals and waste detoxification. Bioremediation that involves the capabilities of microorganisms in the removal of pollutants is the most promising, relatively efficient and cost-effective technology.

Bioremediation experiments on harbor sediments contaminated by aliphatic and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) were investigated by Beolchini *et al.*⁷⁰. It was found that inorganic nutrients stimulated microbial

growth and enhanced the biodegradation of low and high molecular weight hydrocarbons, whereas sand amendment increased only the removal of high molecular weight compounds. Heavy metal bioremediation by a multi-metal resistant endophytic bacteria L14 (EB L14) isolated from the cadmium hyperaccumulator *Solanum nigrum* L. was characterized for its potential application in metal treatment⁷¹. The hormesis of EB L14 were observed in presence of divalent heavy metals Cu^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} at a relatively lower concentration (10 mg/L). The mechanism study indicated that the remediation efficiencies may be greatly promoted through inhibiting the activities of ATPase. The excellent adaptation abilities and promising remediation efficiencies strongly indicated the superiority of this endophyte in heavy metal bioremediation at low concentrations, which could be useful for developing efficient metal removal system.

Green arsenic removal was carried out by EDTA based PLE²⁸ in atmospheric particulate matter, by FI-HGAAS with a heated quartz tube atomizer (QTA) without any kind of sample pretreatment⁵⁴. Diphenylcarbazone-functionalized silica gel was used for on-line solid-phase extraction of green mercury removal in real samples by flow-injection spectrophotometry⁵³. Removal of Cr^{VI} and Cr^{III} in wastewater was achieved with ammonium pyrrolidinedithiocarbamate (APDC) as the chelating agent and the ionic liquid [C₄MIM][PF₆] as the extractant³⁶ whereas mixed-micelle cloud point extraction was used for speciation of chromium⁴⁰ in water samples. PAHs contained in sewage sludge were extracted by a green strategy – PLE²⁹. Rate of biodegradation of PAHs in sediment was influenced by microbial growth which was stimulated by inorganic nutrients⁷⁰.

Activated carbon (AC) can help to overcome toxicity of pollutants to microbes and facilitate soil bioremediation. In this study AC was used for the detoxification of soil from polychlorinated benzenes (PCBs)⁷². A large decrease in bioavailable PCB in AC-amended soils was demonstrated by higher clover germination and biomass. Municipal solid waste (MSW) fly ash is classified as a hazardous material because it contains high amounts of heavy metals. For decontamination, MSW fly ash is first mixed with alkali or alkaline earth metal chlorides (e.g. calcium chloride) and water, and then the mixture is pelletized and treated in a rotary reactor at about 1000 °C; volatile

heavy metal compounds are formed and evaporated⁷³. More than 90% of Cd and Pb and about 60% of Cu and 80% of Zn could be removed by this way. Sub-critical water (sub-CW) technology was used as a new technology with environmental and financial benefits for the recovery of harmful heavy metal ions viz. Cd^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cu^{II}, Fe^{II}, Mn^{II} and Ni^{II} in the waste of Japanese scallop *Patinopecten yessoensis*⁷⁴. This study used sub-CW treatment to recover the metal ions from scallop waste and simultaneously produce harmless and valuable materials. After the sub-CW reaction, four phases existed : an oil phase, metal-soap phase, aqueous phase and solid residual. Both the metal-soap phase and oil phase caught almost all metal ions at low and medium reaction temperatures (473–573 K) from original wastes, although the concentrations of the metal ions in the metal-soap phase were much higher than those in the oil phase. The aqueous phase showed the lowest concentration of metal ions (1.5 ppm) especially at temperatures above 550 K.

Conclusions

This review clearly demonstrates that development of green strategies in analytical chemistry has become an area of intense research. Although it is not always possible to follow totally green schemes and avoid waste production but analytical chemists are exploring existing green methods in analysis and concentrating on developing new green strategies. Detoxification of wastes, when production of hazardous waste production cannot be avoided, is achieved by using green strategies. Analytical chemists all over the world are endeavouring in greening analytical methods to keep our planet safe.

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